

MOTIVATION FOR TEACHING LISTENING AND SPEAKING TO STUDENTS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSES

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Abstract

The article gives the concept of motivation, discusses problems and solutions in the process of teaching listening and speaking to students in foreign language classes, discusses the stimulating reasons that encourage students to be active.

Keywords: motivation, target motivation, success motivation, country-specific motivation, aesthetic motivation, instrumental motivation, communicative competence, educational technologies.

Motivation is an important educational problem, and the teacher needs to interest students so that they learn something new with interest and desire. Almost every teacher periodically has a question: what kind of environment should be created for motivation in the classroom. This question arises especially often when teaching a foreign language at the initial stage, since students have not yet adapted to the requirements of the teacher and the educational institution.

The main goal of the modern concept of education is the socio-cultural adaptation of a person in the world. Currently, it is necessary to teach a "living" language, which means a language in its not just linguistic, but also extralinguistic shell, a language with its behavioral characteristics, when the difference in situations, in partners and linguistic and cultural features of the corresponding national community are taken into account.

Motivation management for learning a foreign language is one of the central problems of teaching methods in higher education. A foreign language as a subject has a number of specific features, one of which is the mastery of a foreign language through the formation and improvement of communication skills.

A.A.Leontiev believes that the motivation of teaching can be determined by external and internal motives [3]. External motives are not related to the content of the educational material: the motive of duty, duties (broad social motives), the motive of evaluation, personal well-being (narrowly social motives), and lack of desire to learn (negative motives). The sources of external motivation may be the following aspects: the desire of students to please their parents, learning a foreign language for general development, for passing the exam successfully, the desire to know a foreign language no worse than their peers, etc. Internal motives, on the contrary, are related to the content of the educational material: motives of cognitive activity, interest in the content of learning, motives for mastering common ways of action, identifying cause-and-effect relationships in the studied educational material (educational and cognitive motives). In other words, a student is interested in a foreign language as such, is interested in foreign language communication and associates his intellectual development with knowledge of a foreign

language. Is it possible to cope with these problems? Is it possible to increase the motivation of students?

There can also be many solutions. Not all problems can be solved at once; many require time and huge efforts to solve. First, you need to identify the group of students who have the lowest motivation. This does not mean that you only need to work with them in the future. All students need the attention and encouragement of the teacher, one should not forget about anyone, but the teacher should place accents. Secondly, I introduce some innovations into classes that were not there before. These can be interesting tasks, business games, etc. As a result, even students with low academic performance show interest in the subject and activity.

I will give a small example from my practice. As a rule, I start my practical classes with a speech charge, which includes both standard phrases previously recorded by students and new ones, which students immediately focus on. If the practical lesson is devoted to grammatical material, then I conduct a role-playing game, the result of which is the consolidation of the material and the successful writing of the test paper. This method is effective because students, even if they have weak knowledge, still involuntarily assimilate the material. Of course, one small game will not be able to change something dramatically. During the lesson, I often encourage students, praise them if they answer correctly, if they get confused somewhere, then I suggest and hint, trying never to pronounce the correct answer myself. I very often ask students to exchange notebooks and check the papers by giving answers on the blackboard. Many people are very pleased to see that in some matters they did not make the mistakes that their neighbor made. At the end of the practical lesson, we summarize the results, analyze the grammatical material, and set ratings that affect the rating. Monthly performance rating is another type of motivation. It is usually conducted in the first year of training and its effectiveness is high as long as students want to gain knowledge. As a result, we can draw a very simple conclusion: the problem of motivation is quite common in all educational institutions and this problem can and should be dealt with by the teacher himself. But only a personality-oriented approach, knowledge of their students, as well as hard work will be able to change the situation.

When students start studying a foreign language, no teacher can complain about their lack of interest in his subject, since this interest is the main force of cognitive activity of students. But according to research, by the 7th grade, the desire to learn a foreign language significantly weakens in 86% of students. Consequently, the teacher needs to master ways to maintain positive motivation to study his subject, a necessary condition for which is the creation of a situation of success in the classroom.

Experiencing a sense of success in communicative activity in foreign language lessons, the student experiences joy, and emotional uplift. The experience of success in educational communication inspires him with self-confidence; self-esteem increases, there is a desire to achieve good results in communicative activity again in order to experience the joy of success once again. If we systematically use methods and techniques that contribute to creating a situation of success in the classroom, the motivation of students to master a foreign language, that is, to develop foreign language communicative competence, will increase. The theoretical basis of the problem of creating a situation of success is: 1) the communicative approach in teaching foreign languages by E.I.Passov; 2) the concepts of A.S.Belkin, E.S.Polat, N.D.Galskova and P.B.Gurvich [1]. Recently the phrase "orientation to success in educational activities" has become familiar. No one disputes the fact that it is positive emotions that can become the most important incentive for a child in educational activities.

K.D.Ushinsky also came to the conclusion that only success supports the student's interest in learning. And interest in learning appears only when there is inspiration born from success in mastering knowledge. A child who has never known the joy of work in learning, who has not experienced pride from the fact that difficulties have been overcome, loses the desire and interest to learn. Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences A.S.Belkin pays great attention to the creation of success situations. He firmly believes that if a child is deprived of faith in himself, it is difficult to hope for his "bright future". One careless word, one ill-considered step of a teacher can break a child so that no educational tricks will help later.

Thus, the student is then drawn to knowledge when he experiences the need for learning, when he is driven by healthy motives and interest, backed up by success. Success in learning is the only source of inner strength of the child, giving birth to energy to overcome difficulties, the desire to learn. In general, a teacher as a person should be interesting to students. If he does not focus only on his subject and he is interested in the life of modern young people, their problems, as well as global problems of society that his students will have to solve in the near future, if the teacher is able to convey and explain his interest to students, then they themselves will strive to communicate with him.

During the lesson, it is necessary to remember about the various types of motivation offered by the Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor P.B. Gurvich.

Target motivation. This motivation is based on a clear awareness of both the ultimate goal of studying and the goal of completing each task, so it is recommended that the student himself formulate the purpose of the lesson, its tasks and ways to solve these tasks. At the end of the lesson, when conducting reflection, it is necessary to focus the attention of students on such issues: "And where can you use the knowledge of today's lesson? In what situations can you use the knowledge gained in the lessons? And so on."

Success motivation. Students want to get something really tangible for the work they have spent, to feel that they are going to the goal. Of course, the mark is the strongest here. And when it is exposed, it is necessary to remember about the zone of the child's closest development. Even a small step towards success should be seen and appreciated. In this case, you can use the method of emotional stimulation.

Country-specific motivation. The fact of moving everyday actions and events to the country of the language being studied increases the interest of students. Comparative analysis and comparison of cultural characteristics of countries allows for a better understanding of purely linguistic phenomena, to model the situations of the Dialogue of Cultures in the lessons. In recent years, this has become especially relevant. The Sample programs in foreign languages talk about strengthening the cultural aspect in the content of education. It is necessary to immerse children in the language environment as often as possible. Listening elements should be present at each lesson, and it should not be just the teacher's speech. Using the Internet allows you to work with German-language sites, which allows you to implement the principle of relevance in the lesson.

Aesthetic motivation. Studying AI for students should turn into a pleasure. Nothing in the classroom or in the classroom should annoy the student. Colorfully designed presentations and booklets contribute to its aesthetic development.

Instrumental motivation. Based on the characteristics of the brain, temperament, types of memory and other aspects of individual differences, each student has his favorite forms and types of work. It is necessary to give each student the opportunity to express himself in his favorite and most successful type of work. The use of various types of computer programs makes it possible to identify his intellectual and creative abilities. By carefully planning the lesson in the lesson system and applying a personality-oriented approach to teaching, the teacher can use the appropriate type of motivation in order to create a situation of success in the lesson, which will be a key factor for the use of other forms and methods of developing students' communicative competence [2].

Thanks to modern pedagogical technologies, the teacher can choose such teaching methods that would allow each student to show their activity, their creativity, such as a business game, project methodology, the use of new information technologies. They help to implement a personality-oriented approach to learning, provide individualization and differentiation of learning taking into account the abilities of students, their

level of learning and creative potential. Using the example of a business game conducted in the classroom, I can say that a business game helps to achieve educational, educational and developmental goals of a collective nature based on familiarity with the real organization of work. The business game has a high cognitive activity, in the process of working on such a lesson, participants become one team, a relationship is established when solving common tasks, and during the game logical thinking develops, the ability to find answers to questions, speech, speech etiquette, the ability to communicate in the process of discussion [4]. So, the formation of motivation has its positive aspects that will help the teacher in the educational process. Moreover, it makes the work in the classroom not only easier for the teacher, but also for students. The main thing is that each work should be properly organized from a methodological point of view.

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